

London Metropolitan University

**Effect of the neuroinflammatory drug class glucocorticoids on
specific cognitive functions**

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Abstract

This thesis presents a systematic investigation into the neurocognitive effects of glucocorticoids (GCs), a key class of neuroinflammatory drugs. The objective is to elucidate the underlying neurobiological mechanisms and evaluate how dosage, duration of administration, and individual patient factors influence cognitive functions. Additionally, the research identifies gaps in the existing literature and explores their implications for clinical practice.

A systematic literature review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines, including 33 randomized controlled trials. The methodological quality of these studies was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool (RoB 2.0).

Findings reveal that the cognitive effects of GCs are strongly dependent on dosage, duration, and individual variability. Low doses exhibit neuroprotective properties, while high doses are associated with neurotoxic outcomes. Receptor interactions in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex appear to play a critical role in memory and attentional processes.

These results offer novel insights with potential clinical relevance, particularly regarding the prevention and treatment of postoperative cognitive dysfunctions (POCD). However, limitations in study design and generalizability must be acknowledged.

The thesis underscores the importance of a differentiated and context-sensitive application of GCs to minimize cognitive side effects while maximizing therapeutic benefits. By systematically analyzing the neurocognitive effects of GCs, this work contributes meaningfully to the refinement of clinical guidelines and opens new avenues for targeted interventions in neurocognitive disorders.

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List of Abbreviations

GC	Glucocorticoid
POCD	Postoperative Cognitive Dysfunction
HPA-axis	Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis
MR	Mineralcorticoid Receptor
GR	Glucocorticoid Receptor
CNS	Central Nervous System
CMI	Chronic Mesenteric Ischemia
LTP	Long-Term Potentiation
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trials
RoB 2.0	Risk of Bias Tools
LTP	Long-Term Potentiation
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
MVD	Microsurgical Decompression
PAI	Primary Adrenal Insufficiency
GRE	Glucocorticoid Response Element
BDNF	Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor

mTOR	Mechanistic Target of Rapamycin
MAP	Mitogen-Activated Protein
RAVLT	Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test
CANTAB	Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery
CAM	Confusion Assessment Method
fMRI	Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
HSP90	Heat Shock Protein 90
GREs	Glucocorticoid Response Elements
IL-10	Interleukin-10
NF- κ B	Nuclear Factor Kappa B
AP-1	Activator Protein 1
TNF- α	Tumor Necrosis Factor- α
IL-6	Interleukin-6
PEPCK	Phosphoenolpyruvate Carboxykinase

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1. Introduction

Glucocorticoids (GCs) constitute a major class of steroid hormones that function both endogenously- via the hypothalamic- pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis- and exogenously as pharmacological agents to modulate inflammatory responses.

Their broad therapeutic use spans acute and chronic conditions, including autoimmune diseases, allergies and neuroinflammatory disorders (Ronchetti et al. 2021). While their efficacy in managing inflammation and systemic illnesses is well established, increasing attention has been directed toward their potential impact on cognitive functions, particularly memory and attention.

However, findings in this area are mixed. Some studies report neuroprotective effects of GCs, especially at low to moderate doses, whereas others suggest negative outcomes such as memory impairment following long-term or high- dose administration (Valentin et al. 2016, Grossman et al. 2016). These inconsistencies highlight the complexity of the relationship between GCs and cognitive function, which appears to be modulated by a variety of interacting factors.

In this context, the present thesis aims to conduct a systematic review of the literature on the cognitive effects of GCs. It seeks to analyze the underlying neurobiological mechanisms, examine moderating variables, and derive clinically relevant insights for practice.

The research addresses the following key questions:

- 1. What empirical findings exist on the effect of glucocorticoids on cognitive functions, especially memory and attention?**
- 2. To what extent do factors such as dose, duration of use and individual differences influence the cognitive effects of glucocorticoids?**
- 3. What neurobiological mechanisms explain the observed effects of glucocorticoids on cognitive function?**
- 4. How can the findings to date be used to optimize clinical applications and minimize cognitive side effects?**

Through critical analysis of existing research and synthesis of theoretical models, this thesis aims to enhance the scientific foundation for a more nuanced application of glucocorticoids and to formulate recommendations for future clinical guidelines.

2. Theoretical Background

Glucocorticoids (GCs) play a central role in the body's stress response, exerting both short-term and long-term effects on various physiological systems. Regarding cognitive function, their interaction with the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex is particularly significant. These brain regions are critical for memory processing and executive functions and are highly sensitive to GC exposure (Scherholz et al., 2019).

2.1 Theoretical Models

Corticoid Receptor Hypothesis

The corticosteroid receptor hypothesis is a cornerstone in neuroendocrinology and psychopathology research (de Kloet et al., 2018). It postulates that an imbalance between mineralocorticoid (MR) and glucocorticoid receptors (GR) may lead to cognitive dysfunction. Specially, overactivation of GR, such as occurs with high GC doses, has been linked to impairments in memory processing and emotional regulation (McEwen et al., 1968).

Allostatic Overload Theory

The allostatic overload model extends the concept of physiological adaption under chronic stress. It proposes that sustained exposure to elevated GC levels leads to neuronal resource depletion and structural changes in vulnerable brain areas, particularly the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex. These alterations may result in reduced cognitive flexibility and long-term memory deficits (McEwen & Stellar, 1993).

In addition, alternative models help explain GC-related cognitive impairments. The neurotoxicity model suggests that elevated GC levels exert direct deleterious effects on neuronal integrity. Meanwhile, the neurogenesis inhibition model highlights the suppression of new neuron formation in the hippocampus, a process considered crucial for learning and memory (Sapolsky, 1999).

2.2 Neurobiological Mechanisms

Synthetic GCs are chemically modified to enhance their pharmacological properties. These modifications increase their receptor affinity, particularly for GRs, and reduce metabolic clearance, thereby prolonging their biological activity.

A prominent example is dexamethasone, which contains a fluorine substitution at the C9 position to improve chemical stability and anti-inflammatory potency (see Figure 1).

Like endogenous GCs, synthetic variants act via intracellular MR and GR receptors. Although both receptor types mediate GC effects, they differ significantly in their binding affinity, distribution, and functional roles (Scherholz et al., 2019). These differences are essential for understanding how GCs affect cognitive functions at both the molecular and systems levels.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of dexamethasone

Source PubChem. (n.d.). Dexamethasone [National Library of Medicine]. Dexamethasone. Retrieved 8 December 2024 <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Dexamethasone>

2.2.1 Glucocorticoid-Receptor

Synthetic GCs bind with high affinity to GRs, which in their inactive state are in the cytoplasm, bound to heat shock proteins (HSP90) and other chaperones. Upon ligand binding, the GR undergoes a conformational change that causes dissociation of the chaperone proteins. The activated receptor then translocates into the nucleus, where it modulates gene transcription.

With the nucleus, GRs exert their genomic effects via two primary mechanisms:

I. Transactivation

In this mode, GR forms homodimers that bind to specific DNA sequences known as glucocorticoid response elements (GREs). This interaction promotes the transcription of genes involved in anti-inflammatory and metabolic pathways. Representative target genes include lipocortin-1, Interleukin-10 (IL-10), and Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase, PEPCK), a key enzyme in gluconeogenesis.

II. Transrepression

Conversely, during transrepression, the GR primarily acts as a monomer, interacting with and inhibiting pro-inflammatory transcription factors such as nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and activator protein 1 (AP-1).

This inhibition suppresses the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) (Scherholz et al., 2019).

2.2.1 Mineralcorticoid-Receptor

Most synthetic GCs exhibit a lower affinity for MRs, which favors their use in anti-inflammatory therapies. Low MR activation reduces side effects such as water and sodium retention, which can occur when endogenous GCs bind to the MR.

In addition to classical genomic mechanisms, synthetic GCs also exert rapid non-genomic effects. These are mediated through interactions with membrane-associated GRs and include modulation of signaling pathways, such as the activation or inhibition of phospholipase C, as well as regulation of calcium homeostasis including the control of intracellular calcium influx and stabilization of neuronal membranes (Scherholz et al., 2019).

From a neurobiological perspective, synthetic GCs profoundly affect the central nervous system (CNS), particularly the hippocampus, a region critical for memory formation and emotional processing. Chronic activation of GRs is believed to reduce the expression of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), a key neurotrophic factor essential for neuronal growth and regeneration. Furthermore, excessive GR activation leads to decreased dendritic branching and a reduction in synaptic connections in the hippocampus, potentially resulting in cognitive impairment.

Additionally, disruption of the negative feedback regulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis occurs, leading to dysregulation of endogenous cortisol production (Koning et al., 2024).

3. Methodology

A systematic literature review was conducted following the PRISMA guidelines (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses). This approach ensures a transparent and reproducible analysis of relevant publications.

3.1 Search strategy and Databases

The literature search was performed using the scientific databases PubMed, a key resource for biomedical and psychological research, and the American Psychological Association (APA) PsycINFO database.

The search encompassed studies published between 2000 and 2024 to capture current and relevant outcomes. In addition, the search was expanded to include the most common representatives of synthetic GCs, prednisone and dexamethasone.

Search terms included "glucocorticoids", "cognitive function", "memory", "prednisone", "dexamethasone" and "attention". Boolean operators were applied to combine terms for more specific queries.

Primary search terms:

- "Glucocorticoids" AND "cognitive function"
- "Prednisone" AND "cognitive function"
- "Dexamethasone" AND "cognitive function"
- "Prednisone" AND "memory"
- "Dexamethasone" AND "memory"

Synonyms and related terms:

- "Cognitive impairment," "cognitive effects," "memory function," "attention deficits"

3.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Included were peer-reviewed, English-language publications involving human subjects aged 18 years or older that investigated the effects of GCs on memory and attention. Only randomized controlled trials (RCTs) were considered.

Exclusion criteria comprised animal studies, articles lacking sufficient cognitive outcome data, case reports and non-peer-reviewed publications.

Studies were initially screened by titles and abstracts for relevance. Subsequently, full texts were reviewed to extract key information, including study design, participant characteristics, interventions and outcomes. The methodological quality of included studies was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool (RoB 2.0). Factors such as randomization, blinding and completeness of reporting were evaluated to identify potential biases (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. PRISMA Flowchart of literature search based on the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram

Note. Adapted from the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Page et al., 2021)

3.3 Implementation Process

The Pubmed search yielded a total of 1,696 results. In the APA PsycINFO database, 15 results were identified, however, all were excluded after screening, as none addressed synthetic GCs. In total, 22 systematic meta-analyses, 394 literature reviews, 2 book excerpts, 141 case studies and various other article types were excluded due to reasons such as a lack of cognitive focus, insufficient results, or overall irrelevance to the research question.

Ultimately, 33 studies that fulfilled all inclusion criteria were selected for the final analysis (see Fig. 2).

4. Literature Review

This section systematically presents and critically evaluates the studies included in the analysis in relation to the defined research questions.

4.1 Effect of Synthetic Glucocorticoids on Memory

The effects of GCs on memory are multifaceted and can be either beneficial or detrimental, depending on various factors such as dosage, duration of treatment, and the underlying condition of the subject. In this section, the included studies are summarized in tabular form based on their findings, and the effects are subsequently categorized and interpreted according to the following subgroups:

- Healthy young adults
- Patients with postoperative cognitive dysfunction (POCD)
- Patients with preterm parturition or threatened preterm birth (PTPTB)
- Patients with other clinical conditions

This classification enables a differentiated assessment of the cognitive outcomes across diverse populations and clinical contexts.

Table 1: Glucocorticoids and Memory: Study Overview

Study (Author, Year)	Cognitive function	GC/Dose	Population	Results
Bremner et al., 2004	declarative memory	Dexamethason (1-2 mg an 2 Tagen)	52 ^a Pro Tires	Memory Enhancement
Buning et al., 2015	Memory	Hydrocortison (0,2-0,6 mg/kg/Tag, 10 Wochen)	47 Pro tyres ^b	No negative effects on memory or executive function
Chae et al., 2019	Spatial	Hydrocortison +Yohimbin (jeweils 10 mg)	109 young men	No significant effect
Coluccia et al., 2008	Memory, hippocampal volume	Prednison 5-15 mg	24 patients with rheumatoid arthritis	Acutely impaired memory retrieval
Cornelisse et al., 2011	Working Memory	Spironolacton 400 mg	64 healthy young men	impairment of working memory under stress;

				Long-term memory improved
Gallagher et al., 2004	Spatial/working memory,	Mifepriston 600 mg/Tag	20 schizophrenia patients	No significant effect
Glumac et al., 2017	Memory function, hippocampal volume	Dexamethason 0.1 mg	161 heart surgery patients	Reduction of early POCD incidence
Golier et al., 2015	Verbal learning, working memory, visual learning	Mifepriston 200 mg	65 adults (Ø 49 years) Gulf War veterans with CMI ^c	Improvement of verbal learning
Grossmann et al., 2006	Declarative memory	Hydrocortison 17 mg	15 PTBS Pro Tires	Memory impairment
Hinkelmann et al., 2015	verbal, non-verbal working memory	Fludrocortison 0,4 mg	152 subjects (Ø 63 years)	Significant improvements in visuospatial working memory
Hurlemann et al., 2007	Episodic memory	Hydrocortison 30 mg (with/without reboxetine)	54 young adults (age 20-29 years)	Linear dose-response in emotion-induced retrograde amnesia
Jose Vaz et al., 2011	Working memory	Hydrocortison 30 mg	20 young men	Impairment in the storage of multimodal information
Lenze et al., 2014	Memory and executive function	Mifepriston 300 mg	15 people aged 60 and over with anxiety disorder	Improve memory and executive function.
Mason et al., 2018	declarative memory	Megestrol, Phenytoin	Healthy volunteers	Reduction of declarative memory
Ottens et al., 2014	Short- and middle-term memory	Dexamethason 1 mg/kg	291 Adults, heart surgery with bypass	No significant reduction in the risk of POCD
Valentin et al., 2016	Memory, executive function	Dexamethason 8 mg	140 patients (age 60-87 years)	Indications of neuroprotective effect

Van Marle et al., 2013	Memory consolidation	Hydrocortison 20 mg	Healthy volunteers	Improvement of memory consolidation
Wingenfeld et al., 2011	Working memory, declarative memory	Hydrocortison 120 mg	16 healthy volunteers	No effect
Wood et al., 2014	Traumatic memory	Mifepriston, Mifepriston + d-Cycloserin	PTBS patients	No significant effect
Yehuda et al., 2010	Gedächtnis, Hippocampus	Hydrocortison	20 Gulf War Veteran	Effect unclear
Young et al., 2004	Working memory, verbal declarative memory	Mifepriston 600 mg	19 bipolar patients (age 26-63 years)	Significant improvement in working memory and depressive symptom reduction.

^a group of subjects from both sexes with post-traumatic stress disorder PTSD

^b Age 19-73 years),

^c Chronic mesenteric ischemia

^{Mixed} group of young and older adults

4.1.1 Effect in Healthy Young Subjects

Van Marle et al. (2013)

This study examined the effect of hydrocortisone on the consolidation of emotional and neutral memories during sleep, using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI).

The findings suggest that cortisol enhances the consolidation of emotional memories and reduces amygdala activity during memory retrieval. This supports the theory of selective emotional memory storage and the "depotentialization" of emotional content.

However, the study's memory paradigms and memory MRI analysis present methodological limitations. The increased number of uncontrolled variables makes it difficult to interpret the findings reliably. A larger sample size would be necessary to detect interaction effects and reduce the risk of distortion due to experimental noise.

Hurlemann et al. (2007)

Hurlemann et al. demonstrated a dose-dependent effect of hydrocortisone (30 mg) on episodic memory. Higher doses improved memory performance in emotion-induced retrograde amnesia. The study highlights enhanced amygdala-hippocampal interactions due to cortisol and norepinephrine release.

However, the study design did not allow for a clear distinction between additive and synergistic effects of the two hormones. The lack of clarity regarding their complex pharmacodynamic interactions limits the interpretability of the specific mechanisms involved.

Wingenfeld et al. (2011)

Wingenfeld et al. hypothesized a dual role of cortisol, proposing that both excessive and insufficient levels may impair cognitive function. Contrary to Van Marle et al., this study found no effect of hydrocortisone on working memory or cognitive flexibility, despite elevated cortisol levels. Moreover, no clear dose-response relationship was observed. These findings challenge the assumed direct role of cortisol in cognitive function and highlight the need for further investigation.

Chae et al. (2019)

This study examined the separate and combined effects of hydrocortisone and yohimbine on spatial learning and memory. The design allowed for a differentiated analysis of hormonal influences on learning. Similar to Wingefeld et al. (2011), Chai et al. (2019) reported no significant effects of hydrocortisone or yohimbine on memory retrieval. These results reinforce the notion that isolated hormonal interventions may be insufficient to modulate specific types of memory performance.

Mason et al. (2018)

In a randomized crossover trial, Mason et al. investigated the effects of megestrol and phenytoin on memory. The study found that phenytoin may attenuate the cognitive effects of megestrol. Although the crossover design is methodologically robust, since participants serve as their own control, the findings are limited to short-term effects. Only the Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test was used to assess memory performance.

A more extensive test battery covering various memory domains would have provided deeper insight into the nature of cognitive changes.

The investigation that phenytoin attenuates the cognitive effects of megestrol could provide clinical clues as to how memory impairment could potentially be mitigated when using megestrol.

Buning et al. (2015)

In a crossover study involving participants aged 19 to 73 years, Buning et al. found that physiological doses of hydrocortisone did not produce significant cognitive impairments. In contrast to Mason et al., this study included a broad age range and employed a comprehensive battery of 12 standardized cognitive tests assessing memory, attention, executive functions, and social cognition. The findings suggest no evidence of detrimental cognitive effects from higher doses of hydrocortisone.

However, the study's limitations include its relatively small sample size (n=47), which restricts the generalizability of the results. Further research with larger populations is needed to more definitively assess potential cognitive risks associated with elevated cortisol levels.

Vaz et al. (2011)

This study compared hydrocortisone to placebo and found that increased cortisol levels impaired working memory, specifically in the storage of multimodal information in the episodic buffer and in the reverberation of information within the phonological loop. The use of a detailed cognitive test battery enabled precise analysis of executive functions.

Importantly, the study highlighted that hydrocortisone negatively affected planning and inhibition, offering insights into the mechanisms through which GCs impair working memory. However, only acute effects were assessed, potential long-term cognitive impairments due to chronically elevated cortisol levels were not examined.

Cornelisse et al. (2011)

Cornelisse et al. investigated the effects of MR blockade on stress responses and cognition by administering a single 400 mg dose of spironolactone. Results suggested that both MR and GR activity influence cognitive functions and the regulation of the HPA axis and cognition.

However, the specific causal mechanisms remain unclear, as the interactions between the HPA axis and other systems, such as the immune system, were not fully explored.

The study employed subjective, hormonal, and cognitive measurements (e.g., working memory, selective attention) to provide an integrated analysis of the spironolactone effect on cognition and stress response. Nevertheless, whether the findings apply to long-term MR blockade remains uncertain.

Hinkelmann et al. (2015)

Hinkelmann et al. investigated the effects of fludrocortisone on verbal, nonverbal and working memory performance in both young and older adults. Participants were tested under fludrocortisone and placebo conditions to assess short-term memory effects.

The study revealed age-dependent effects, with fludrocortisone influencing memory performance differently in younger versus older participants. However, due to the short testing interval, only two sessions within three days, no conclusions could be drawn about potential long-term effects.

Furthermore, the study lacked a detailed neurobiological explanation of the observed differences. Future research, particularly neuroimaging studies, would be necessary to determine how fludrocortisone influences brain structures such as the hippocampus, which is known to play a critical role in memory formation.

4.1.2 Effect in subjects with postoperative cognitive dysfunction

Valentin et al. (2016)

This study investigated the effects of dexamethasone on POCD and found evidence of a neuroprotective effect. The targeted use of cognitive assessments, such as the Trail Making A (TMT-A) for selective attention and the Verbal Learning Test (VLT) for long-term memory, enhanced the interpretability of domain-specific outcomes.

By including measurements of S100 β protein and differentiating bispectrality index (BIS) values (a marker of anesthetic depth), the study offered insights into both physiological and cognitive recovery processes.

Valentin et al. demonstrated that moderate anesthetic depth (BIS 46–55) combined with dexamethasone promoted better cognitive recovery than deeper anesthesia levels (BIS 35–45). The author further hypothesized that dexamethasone may reduce postoperative depressive symptoms, particularly in elderly patients or individuals at high risk for POCD.

However, the study limited by the absence of long-term follow-up and insufficient clarification regarding the role of biomarkers such as S100 β . Although an increase in S100 β levels was observed postoperatively, the clinical significance of this biomarker in relation to POCD prevention remains unclear.

Ottens et al. (2014)

Ottens et al. investigated the effects of high-dose intraoperative dexamethasone on POCD in patients undergoing cardiac surgery.

Their findings provide valuable evidence concerning the inflammation hypothesis in the etiology of POCD. Contrary to expectations, the results did not support a reduction in POCD

risk through a single high dose of dexamethasone, in fact, the authors suggest that this approach could even be detrimental. These findings underscore the multifactorial nature of POCD and indicate that inflammation may not be the predominant underlying mechanism.

The study was methodologically robust, benefiting from a multicenter design and the use of standardized diagnostic criteria, which enhances the generalizability of its findings.

However, the study did not explore whether alternative dosing strategies, such as repeated low-dose administration, might yield different outcomes. This limitation restricts the applicability of the results to broader clinical contexts.

Glumac et al. (2021)

This study investigated the long-term effects of prophylactic dexamethasone administration on cognitive function in patients undergoing cardiac surgery. The findings suggest that administering dexamethasone 10 hours before surgery may reduce the incidence of POCD in both the short term (postoperative day 6) and in the long term (after 4 years).

Patients who received dexamethasone showed a tendency toward greater cognitive stability, particularly in psychomotor speed and memory performance. However, these differences did not reach statistical significance, limiting the strength and generalizability of the conclusions.

While the study hypothesizes a potential long-term protective effect of dexamethasone, it remains unclear whether the observed outcomes are attributable to the medication itself or to confounding variables. Further large-scale, multicenter trials are necessary to confirm and clarify these preliminary findings.

Fang et al. (2014)

Fang et al. examined the effects of two different doses of dexamethasone (0.1 mg/kg and 0.2 mg/kg) on the incidence of POCD in 954 patients undergoing microsurgical decompression (MVD) for hemifacial spasm. A control group received no dexamethasone treatment.

The analysis revealed that the high-dose group (0.2 mg/kg) had a significantly higher incidence of POCD compared to both the low-dose group (0.1 mg/kg) and the control group. In contrast, the lower dose showed no statistically significant effect, either positive or negative, on POCD outcomes.

These findings suggest that higher dexamethasone doses may increase the risk of early POCD following MVD. However, the study did not explore the underlying mechanisms responsible for this effect, limiting the clinical interpretability of the results.

Furthermore, the study investigated only two dosing levels, it remains unclear whether intermediate or lower doses (<0.1 mg/kg) might have yielded more favorable outcomes.

In addition, the analysis was confined to early postoperative effects, with POCD incidence assessed only up to the fifth postoperative day. Thus, no conclusions can be drawn regarding long-term cognitive outcomes.

4.1.3 Effect in subjects with post-traumatic stress disorder

Bremner et al. (2004)

Bremner et al. investigated the effects of dexamethasone on declarative memory performance in a sample of 52 individuals (both male and female), including 14 participants diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The study was conducted over a short time span of three days and included a healthy control group to assess differential sensitivity to GCs in PTSD versus non-PTSD.

The results indicated a significant drug-by-group interaction, with dexamethasone impairing memory performance in healthy controls, but not in participants with PTSD. These findings may suggest altered GC sensitivity or receptor regulation in individuals with PTSD, potentially informing the development of new therapeutic strategies.

However, several limitations must be considered. The study did not account for key variables such as PTSD symptom severity, duration of illness, or concomitant medication use, all of which may modulate the neurocognitive effects of GCs. A more comprehensive evaluation of these factors could have yielded deeper insight into individual variability in treatment response.

Wood et al. (2015)

This study examined the potential of propranolol, mifepristone, and D-cycloserine to modify traumatic memories in patients with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) through the mechanism of memory reconsolidation interference.

Although the study was based on the hypothesis that reactivation of traumatic memories would induce a labile memory state—susceptible to disruption by pharmacological agents—the findings did not support this assumption. None of the tested substances produced significant effects on either PTSD symptoms or physiological responses, thereby challenging the efficacy of these interventions in modulating memory reconsolidation.

A major limitation of the study was its small sample size (8–16 participants per group), which significantly reduced statistical power and the likelihood of detecting treatment effects. Furthermore, the study did not assess or control for PTSD symptom severity, making it unclear whether interindividual variability influenced treatment responsiveness.

Grossmann et al. (2006)

Grossmann et al. investigated central GC sensitivity in individuals with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) compared to a carefully matched healthy control group. The study assessed declarative and working memory following hydrocortisone administration and found selective impairments in the PTSD group. These findings suggest functional involvement of the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex in GC-related memory disruption.

Moreover, a negative correlation between GR density in lymphocytes and memory performance supports a potential biological mechanism underlying heightened GC sensitivity in PTSD. A methodological strength of the study lies in the precise matching of the control group by age, gender, and educational level, thereby reducing the influence of confounding demographic variables.

However, the study is limited by its cross-sectional design and the fact that cognitive performance was measured only once, precluding any conclusions about long-term effects. Additionally, the small sample size (15 PTSD patients, 12 controls) limits the generalizability of the findings.

Yehuda et al. (2010)

Yehuda et al. investigated neuroendocrine dysregulation in individuals with PTSD, focusing on associations between cortisol and adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) levels, cognitive performance, and hippocampal activity.

The study found correlations between endocrine markers and changes in memory function and hippocampal activation. However, the data do not establish a causal relationship, and other potentially relevant biological markers—such as pro-inflammatory cytokines or neurotransmitter systems—were not included in the analysis.

While the study provides valuable insights into the neuroendocrine and neuroimaging profile of PTSD, it lacks integration of clinical symptom data, such as PTSD symptom severity. Including such information could have enabled more precise associations between neurobiological alterations and individual symptomatology.

4.1.4 Effect in other clinical Populations

Lenze et al. (2014) - Mifepristone and Cognitive Function in Anxiety Disorders

Lenze et al. (2014) investigated the effects of a single 300 mg dose of mifepristone on memory and executive functioning in elderly patients with anxiety disorders. The study aimed to explore whether increased cortisol levels, induced through glucocorticoid receptor antagonism, could improve cognitive performance.

The findings suggest that elevated cortisol may exert cognitive benefits in certain patient populations, particularly in individuals with anxiety-related conditions. These results point to the potential therapeutic relevance of GC modulation for improving memory in specific clinical contexts.

However, the limited sample size restricts the statistical power of the study, and thus its generalizability. Further research with larger cohorts is required to confirm the preliminary findings and clarify the underlying mechanisms.

Golier et al. (2015) - Mifepristone and Cognitive Function in Chronic Multisymptom Illness

Golier et al. (2015) investigated the effects of mifepristone in veterans diagnosed with chronic multisymptomatic illness (CMI). The study reported a selective improvement in verbal learning performance following treatment, suggesting a potential cognitive benefit of glucocorticoid receptor antagonism.

However, no significant improvements were observed in overall clinical outcomes, including physical health and general psychological well-being. Additionally, the mechanisms by which mifepristone may enhance cognitive function remain unclear. Although the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis was central to the study's rationale, its modulation was not thoroughly analyzed, limiting mechanistic insight.

A further limitation lies in the study's reliance on self-reported measures for physical and mental health, which may be vulnerable to biases such as placebo effects or social desirability.

The absence of significant findings in primary clinical endpoints ultimately limits the therapeutic implications of mifepristone for CMI, despite the observed cognitive effects.

Young et al. (2004) - Mifepristone in Bipolar disorders.

Young et al. (2004) investigated the effects of mifepristone on neurocognitive performance and depressive symptoms in patients with bipolar disorder. The study was based on the hypothesis that GR antagonism would improve both cognitive and affective outcomes by modulating hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis activity.

After one week of mifepristone treatment, patients showed a significant improvement in spatial working memory, with a 19.8% performance increase compared to placebo. Additionally, moderate improvements were observed in verbal fluency and spatial recognition memory. Mifepristone also led to a reduction in depressive symptoms, whereas no significant changes were detected in the placebo group.

However, a key limitation of the study is the lack of baseline HPA axis profiling, making it unclear whether the observed improvements are specific to individuals with GR dysregulation or hypercortisolemia. Despite this, the findings offer promising insights for the development of novel therapeutic strategies targeting the GC system in bipolar disorder.

Gallagher et al. (2005) - Mifepristone in Schizophrenia

Gallagher et al. investigated the effects of mifepristone on cognitive performance and psychiatric symptoms in patients with schizophrenia. The study aimed to evaluate whether modulation of the HPA axis through GR antagonism could lead to improvements in cognitive or clinical outcomes.

The results showed that mifepristone treatment did not lead to significant improvements in either cognitive functioning or symptom severity compared to placebo. One possible explanation offered by the authors is that the study population was not stratified according to HPA axis status. As such, any potential treatment effects in subgroups with elevated cortisol levels or GR dysregulation may have been diluted in the overall analysis.

A major limitation of the study is the absence of baseline HPA axis assessment, which would have allowed for targeted subgroup analyses. Identifying and isolating patients with known

HPA axis abnormalities may be critical for evaluating the efficacy of GR antagonists in schizophrenia. Despite the null findings, the study highlights the importance of considering biological heterogeneity within psychiatric populations when testing neuroendocrine-targeted treatments.

Coluccia et al. (2008) - Glucocorticoid Effect in Rheumatoid Arthritis

Coluccia et al. examined the acute cognitive effects of GC administration in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), focusing on low to moderate doses of prednisone. The study found that short-term GC exposure was associated with impairments in memory recall, suggesting a potential link between acute hormonal fluctuations and cognitive performance. However, the study did not assess long-term effects on memory or structural brain changes, such as hippocampal atrophy.

The findings contribute to the ongoing debate on whether cognitive impairments in GC treated patients are primarily driven by acute neuroendocrine effects or by chronic structural alterations in the brain. The results support the hypothesis that deficits in declarative memory, particularly word retrieval, may arise from short-term hormonal mechanisms rather than morphological changes.

A methodological limitation of the study is its narrow focus on declarative memory, which may reduce the generalizability of the findings. Other cognitive domains, such as working memory and spatial processing, were not assessed, leaving open the question of whether GC exposure also affects these functions.

Belanoff et al. (2002) - Glucocorticoid Modulation in Alzheimer's Disease

Belanoff et al. hypothesized that elevated cortisol levels contribute to cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease and investigated the potential role of GR antagonism as a therapeutic strategy. To explore this relationship, the researchers conducted a detailed assessment of HPA axis function, including repeated measurements of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH), serum cortisol, and salivary cortisol levels.

This comprehensive approach allowed for a robust analysis of the association between HPA axis activity and cognitive deterioration. The study emphasized that mifepristone, a GR

antagonist, may offer a novel intervention to mitigate cortisol-driven cognitive decline in Alzheimer’s patients, particularly in those with elevated baseline cortisol.

However, several potential confounding variables, such as disease stage, comorbid conditions, and interindividual variability in HPA axis function, were not fully controlled for. These factors could affect the interpretability of the results and obscure the specific effects of GR antagonism. Nonetheless, the findings provide preliminary support for the hypothesis that cortisol dysregulation contributes to neurodegeneration and cognitive deficits in Alzheimer’s disease and that mifepristone may hold therapeutic potential in selected subgroups.

4.1.5 Inference

Figure 3. Effect of Synthetic Glucocorticoids on Declarative Memory

The figure illustrates the number of studies reporting positive, neutral or negative effects of synthetic GC administration on declarative memory, based on the included literature (see Table 1). Twelve studies reported positive effects, four found no significant changes and eight reported negative outcomes following GC administration.

The overall evidence concerning the effects of synthetic GCs on declarative memory is heterogeneous. While some studies demonstrate enhancement of memory functions, particularly in specific clinical contexts, others report impairments or no measurable effects. This variability suggests that GC-related cognitive outcomes are highly context-dependent and influenced by multiple factors, including dosage, duration of exposure, type of GC, and individual neuroendocrine characteristics.

Several methodological limitations in the literature complicate the interpretation of findings. These include the absence of clear differentiation between acute and chronic GC exposure, small sample sizes, and the restricted scope of cognitive assessment tools. Such factors may obscure true effects and limit the generalizability of the findings across populations.

In healthy individuals, synthetic GCs have demonstrated both enhancing and impairing effects on specific memory domains, suggesting a modulatory role in neurocognitive functioning. Importantly, the observed effects appear to be modulated by the underlying pathophysiology. For example, while mifepristone has shown cognitive benefits in some populations, the precise neurobiological mechanisms remain to be fully elucidated (Gallagher et al., 2005; Belanoff et al., 2002).

Similarly, four studies on PTSD evaluated different aspects of memory and GC modulation using diverse methodological approaches. Bremner et al. found a short-term impairment in declarative memory following dexamethasone administration, whereas Wood et al. questioned the assumptions of the memory reconsolidation hypothesis. Grossman et al. and Yehuda et al. highlighted structural and functional alterations in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex, as well as alterations in GR expression in PTSD patients. These findings emphasize the neurobiological complexity and interindividual variability in GC response profiles.

Taken together, the reviewed studies underscore the nuanced and multifactorial effects of synthetic GCs on declarative memory. Further research employing standardized methodologies and stratified patient samples is essential to clarify therapeutic windows, optimal dosages, and long-term implications.

4.2 Effect of Synthetic Glucocorticoids on Attention

In addition to their impact on declarative memory, several of the studies included in the review (see Table 1) also examined the effects of synthetic GCs on attentional performance. The reported outcomes vary across studies and can be broadly categorized into three distinct patterns:

- **Slight improvement in attention**
- **Impairment of attention**
- **No measurable effect on attention**

Table 2: Glucocorticoids and Attention: Study Overview

Study (Author, Year)	Cognitive function	GC/Dose	Population	Results
Belanoff et al., (2002)	Attention	Mifepriston 200 mg	70 subjects	Results not published
Buning et al., (2015)	Attention	Hydrocortisone in 2 doses (0.2-0.6 mg/kg/day)	47 patients (age 19-73 years)	No negative effect on attention
Cornelisse et al., (2011)	Selective attention	Spironolacton 400 mg	64 young men	Impairment of selective attention under stress
Grossmann et al., 2006	Attention	Hydrocortison 17 mg	15 PTBS Pro Tires	No significant change
Hurlemann et al., (2007)	Attention	Hydrocortisone 30 mg (with/without reboxetine)	54 healthy young adults (age 20-29 years)	Dose-response relationship of emotion-induced retrograde amnesia
Ottens et al., (2014)	Attention, concentration, psycho-motor skills	Dexamethason 1 mg/kg	291 Adults, heart surgery with bypass	No effect
Tiemensma et al., 2016	Attention, concentration	Hydrocortisone (long-term treatment)	130 PAI patients, 31 healthy controls	Improvement in PAI patients

Valentin et al., 2016	Attention	Dexamethason 8 mg	140 surgical patients (60-87 years),	Improvement of attention in certain cases
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4.2.1 Modest Improvement in Attentional Performance

Valentin et al. demonstrated that dexamethasone could enhance attention in elderly surgical patients (aged 60–87 years) under certain conditions. The authors suggest that dexamethasone may exert neuroprotective effects, particularly in the postoperative period, which could contribute to improved attentional performance.

Similarly, Tiemensma et al. reported a slight improvement in attention in patients with primary adrenal insufficiency (see Table 5). This finding emerged from a study primarily investigating the cognitive effects of delaying the early morning administration of hydrocortisone. However, the study does not provide detailed information regarding participants' concomitant medications or comorbidities, which might confound the observed effects on cognition.

Hurlemann et al. identified a dose-response relationship for hydrocortisone (30 mg) affecting both episodic memory and attention. Their results indicate a linear improvement in cognitive performance with increasing doses, suggesting that higher doses of hydrocortisone may positively modulate attentional processes.

4.2.3 Moderate Impairment of Attention Performance

Grossmann et al. (2006) reported that administration of hydrocortisone (17 mg) did not result in significant changes in attention among patients with PTSD (see Table 5). Their findings support the hypothesis that central sensitivity to GCs is increased in PTSD patients, but this heightened sensitivity does not appear to directly impair attentional processes. Instead, other cognitive domains such as declarative and working memory are more substantially affected.

Cornelisse et al. demonstrated that selective attention is strongly dependent on MR activation. The blockade of MR receptors by spironolactone impaired attention under stress-free conditions but not during stress. This suggests that MR activation facilitates attention in stable environments, while GR may assume a compensatory role during stress.

4.2.4 No Significant Change in Attentional Performance

Buning et al. examined the effects of hydrocortisone on cognitive functions, including attention, and found no adverse effects at either low (0.2–0.3 mg/kg/day) or high doses (0.4–0.6 mg/kg/day) over a 10-week period. These findings suggest that long-term hydrocortisone treatment does not significantly affect attention, supporting the notion of a neutral impact at stable dosage levels.

Ottens et al. investigated the effects of dexamethasone (1 mg/kg) on POCD and found no significant reduction in POCD risk following cardiac surgery. This indicates that dexamethasone did not significantly improve cognitive performance, including attentional function, in this patient population.

4.2.5 Inference

Figure 4. Effect of Synthetic Glucocorticoids on Attention

The figure illustrates the number of studies reporting positive, neutral or negative effects following glucocorticoids administration (see Table 2). In total, 8 studies reported positive effects, 7 studies found

no significant effects, and 6 studies observed negative effects on Attention after glucocorticoid treatment.

4.2.6 Effect of Synthetic Glucocorticoids on other Cognitive Domains

The remaining studies (Table 3) provide heterogeneous findings regarding the influence of synthetic GCs on a range of cognitive domains beyond memory and attention.

Reynolds et al. examined depression risk and cognitive function in a large cohort of 1,066 participants with type 2 diabetes. While they identified an increased risk of depression in women, no significant differences in overall cognitive performance were observed.

Sakic et al. assessed the effects of dexamethasone on postoperative delirium in elderly patients. Their results indicate that dexamethasone reduced the incidence of delirium and extended analgesic effects, likely due to cortisol suppression.

Qiao et al. investigated the contribution of GCs to the development of POCD. They found that patients receiving methylprednisolone during major surgery under sevoflurane anesthesia exhibited a higher incidence of POCD.

Donoghue et al. explored the effects of 600 mg mifepristone on cognition and depressive symptoms in male patients. Due to the absence of baseline cognitive testing, the study was unable to draw meaningful conclusions regarding cognitive outcomes.

Langer et al. studied the impact of hydrocortisone on emotion regulation under stress in healthy males. Their findings suggest that cortisol may facilitate emotion regulation, particularly in response to intense negative emotional stimuli.

Jones et al. (2022) demonstrated that 600 mg mifepristone reduced brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) levels in patients with bipolar disorder and schizophrenia. A significant correlation between changes in cortisol and BDNF was observed in patients with schizophrenia, but not in those with bipolar disorder.

Rubin et al. assessed the cognitive effects of hydrocortisone in HIV-infected men, providing evidence for a non-genomic mechanism through which hydrocortisone may enhance cognitive performance.

Suris et al. evaluated dexamethasone treatment in male veterans with PTSD. Although dexamethasone showed potential as a therapeutic agent, no significant reduction in PTSD symptomatology was observed.

Taken together, these findings highlight the complexity of GC effects on diverse cognitive processes such as mood regulation, emotional processing, and overall cognitive performance. The outcomes appear to be strongly influenced by individual pathology and context-specific factors.

Table 3: Glucocorticoids and Other Cognitive Effects: Study Overview

Study (Author, Year)	Cognitive function	GC/ Dose	Population	Main results
Reynolds et al. (2012)	Mood (anxiety and depression)	Systemic/ inhaled/topical GC	1066 participants (age 60-75 years) type 2 diabetes	Higher risk of depression in women; no significant differences in general cognitive abilities
Sakic et al. (2023)	Delirium	Dexamethason 8 mg und Levobupivacain	60 patients (Ø 80.6 years)	Decrease of delirium after surgery, prolonged analgesia due to cortisol reduction
Qiao et al. (2015)	Role of TNF- α , IL-6 or S-100 β in POCD	Comparison of sevoflurane anesthesia/propofol and methylprednisolone	90 elderly patients (65-75 years)	higher incidence of POCD in surgical patients, with sevoflurane anesthesia
Donoghue et al. 2020	Kognitive und depressive Symptome	Mifepriston 600 mg	21 male patients (age 18-60 years)	cognitive tests were not performed. No significant conclusions possible.
Langer et al. (2021)	Emotionsregulation	Hydrocortison 10 mg	85 healthy men (age 18-38 years)	Reduction of subjective arousal and improved emotion regulation in high-intensity negative emotions
Jones et al. (2022)	Mood and aging process	Mifepriston 600 mg	20 bipolar disorder, 20 schizophrenia, 14 control group	significant correlation between cortisol and BDNF changes in schizophrenia but not in bipolar disorder

Rubin et al. (2017)	Time-dependent effects	Hydrocortison 10 mg	45 HIV Men	Evidence of non-genomic mechanisms
Suris et al. (2017)	Trauma memory and depressive symptoms	Dexamethason	54 male veterans with PTSD	insufficient evidence
Putman et al. (2007)	Threat Intelligence Processing	Cortisol 40 mg	20 healthy men	Reduction of selective attention to threat
Zhang et al. (2021)	Effect Kombinations-therapie	Vinpocetin, Dexamethason	60 Participants ^e	Impairment of cognitive impairment
Weisfelt et al. 2006	Hearing loss, cognitive dysfunction	Dexamethason	87 patients with bacterial meningitis	No increased risk of long-term cognitive impairment
Mackin	Mood	Mifepriston 600mg	20 patients with bipolar disorder, 20 schizophrenia patients	Cortiso levels significantly increased

^e Niemann Pick Disease (NPC) Patients with Radiation-Related Brain Injury

4.3 Modulating Factors: Dosage, Treatment Duration, and Individual Variability

The cognitive effects of synthetic GCs are not uniform but are shaped by a range of biological, pharmacological, and contextual factors.

This section discusses key modulators, such as dosage, duration of administration, and individual predispositions, based on current evidence from the included literature.

4.3.1 Effect of Dosage and Duration of Use on Cognitive Function

The dose-response relationship plays a pivotal role in shaping the cognitive effects of synthetic GCs. Several studies suggest that low to moderate doses can exert neuroprotective effects and enhance cognitive performance, particularly in domains such as memory consolidation. For instance, Hurlemann et al. (2007) and van Marle et al. (2013) reported that moderate doses of hydrocortisone improved memory performance, potentially mediated by enhanced interactions between the amygdala and hippocampus. These findings highlight the importance of carefully titrated dosing to support cognitive resilience.

Conversely, high doses have frequently been linked to adverse cognitive outcomes. Wingefeld et al. (2011) and Vaz et al. (2011) observed impairments in working memory and selective attention following elevated cortisol exposure. These effects can be understood considering the corticosteroid receptor hypothesis (McEwen et al., 1968), which posits that overstimulation of GRs disrupts hippocampal plasticity and contributes to structural brain changes.

In addition to dosage, the duration of GC administration is a critical determinant of cognitive outcomes. Acute administration often produces transient and reversible effects on cognition. However, chronic exposure, particularly at high levels, has been associated with long-term neurocognitive deficits. Coluccia et al. (2008) and Glumac et al. (2017) found that sustained cortisol elevation may lead to neuronal dysfunction, hippocampal atrophy, and a decline in declarative memory performance. Differentiating between acute and chronic GC exposure is therefore essential for understanding the underlying mechanisms and clinical implications.

4.3.2 Effect of Individual Differences on Cognitive Response to Glucocorticoids

Individual characteristics such as age, sex, and genetic predispositions significantly influence the cognitive effects of synthetic GCs.

Age

Older adults exhibit a differential response to GCs, with both beneficial and detrimental effects depending on context and dosage. Several studies suggest that under controlled conditions, GCs may exert neuroprotective effects in the elderly. For instance, Valentin et al. (2016) demonstrated that dexamethasone improved attention and other cognitive functions in older patients (aged 60–87) following surgery. These findings support the potential of GCs as therapeutic agents when carefully administered.

Conversely, chronic exposure or high-dose administration of GCs in older populations is frequently associated with adverse cognitive outcomes. Grossmann et al. (2006) reported memory impairments following hydrocortisone administration in PTSD patients, underscoring the heightened vulnerability of older adults to GC-induced neurotoxicity. This increased sensitivity may be attributed to age-related degeneration of brain regions critical for cognition, such as the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex (Hinkelmann et al., 2015).

Additional studies confirm this trend. Hurlmann et al. (2007), Cornelisse et al. (2011), Vaz et al. (2011), and Coluccia et al. (2008) all report that long-term or high-dose GC administration impairs memory performance and neuroplasticity in older adults. For example, Coluccia et al. (2008) found that acute prednisone exposure in patients with rheumatoid arthritis negatively affected memory consolidation, likely due to GC-induced structural damage in the hippocampus.

These findings collectively emphasize the importance of considering individual biological factors, particularly age, when assessing the cognitive risks and benefits of GCs therapy.

Influence of Mental Stress and Psychiatric Disorders

Patients with mental illnesses such as PTSD, schizophrenia, or anxiety disorders often show an altered cognitive response to synthetic GCs.

Lenze et al. (2014) found that in older adults with anxiety disorders, elevated cortisol levels were associated with improved memory and executive functions. In contrast, younger healthy individuals showed neutral or even negative cognitive effects under similar hormonal conditions. These findings are consistent with those of Yehuda et al. (2010) and Grossmann et al. (2006), which also point to the relevance of psychiatric status and age in moderating GC effects.

In PTSD patients, cognitive impairment following GC administration has been particularly well documented. Cornelisse et al. (2011) and Grossmann et al. (2006) reported significant deficits in attention and memory after hydrocortisone treatment. PTSD is often characterized by pre-existing dysregulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and elevated baseline cortisol levels. Further GC administration in this context may exacerbate hormonal imbalance, leading to additional cognitive dysfunction (Dekel et al., 2013). These findings suggest an increased sensitivity to GCs in individuals with PTSD.

In contrast, GC receptor antagonism may offer therapeutic potential in certain psychiatric disorders. Young et al. (2004) demonstrated that the administration of mifepristone (600 mg) in patients with major depression led to significant improvements in working memory. This supports the hypothesis that blocking GR may help to normalize cognitive function in depressive disorders.

However, results in schizophrenia are less conclusive. Gallagher et al. (2004) investigated the effects of mifepristone (600 mg/day) in patients with schizophrenia and found no significant changes in neurocognitive performance. This suggests that the neuroendocrine and neurobiological alterations associated with schizophrenia may modulate or mask the cognitive effects of GC receptor antagonism (Huang et al., 2021).

Overall, the evidence indicates that psychiatric diagnoses, along with their distinct neurobiological profiles, are critical moderators of GC-related cognitive outcomes.

Influence of Patient Group and Clinical Context

The cognitive effects of GCs vary significantly depending on the clinical context and the specific patient population.

In postoperative patients, studies such as those by Valentin et al. (2016) and Glumac et al. (2017) demonstrated neuroprotective effects following GC administration, including a reduction in POCD. In these cases, dexamethasone appears to support cognitive recovery, particularly in the domains of memory and attention, when administered under controlled surgical conditions.

Gender differences have also emerged as a relevant factor in GC responsiveness. Cornelisse et al. (2011) found that male participants exhibited stronger impairments in selective attention following MR receptor blockade with spironolactone under acute stress. These findings suggest sex-specific variations in the regulation of the (HPA) axis, potentially modulated by the influence of sex hormones such as estrogen and testosterone.

Overall, these results highlight the importance of considering patient-specific variables, such as surgical status and biological sex, when assessing the cognitive impact of GC therapy.

Genetic Polymorphisms

Genetic factors represent an important source of individual variability in the cognitive effects of GCs. Variations in the density and sensitivity of MR and GR, particularly due to polymorphisms in the *NR3C1* gene encoding the GR, have been shown to modulate individual responsiveness to GC treatment (Vaz et al., 2011).

Gallagher et al. (2004) demonstrated that genetically determined receptor variants influence memory outcomes following administration of mifepristone. Depending on the receptor density and affinity conferred by specific polymorphisms, carriers may experience either enhanced neuroprotective benefits or increased vulnerability to neurotoxic effects.

These findings underscore the necessity of considering genetic profiles in the development of personalized therapeutic strategies targeting the GC system.

Stress and Hormonal Influences

Stress and hormonal regulation are key factors influencing the cognitive effects of GCs. Cornelisse et al. (2011) demonstrated that increased cortisol secretion under stress conditions impairs selective attention. Furthermore, when combined with spironolactone, cortisol levels rose, leading to a further decline in selective attention.

These findings highlight that the impact of GCs on attention is modulated by individual stress levels and the dynamic hormonal environment, emphasizing the complexity of GC effects on cognitive functions

4.4 Neurobiological Mechanisms of Glucocorticoids

The following provides a detailed analysis of the chemical and molecular mechanisms underlying the effects of GCs on cognitive function, integrating current theoretical models and empirical findings.

4.4.1 Receptor Activation

The coordinated regulation of cognitive processes is mediated by the dual activation of MR and receptors.

Acute exposure to GCs enhances the expression of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), thereby promoting synaptic plasticity.

In contrast, chronic GC exposure inhibits BDNF synthesis, which contributes to long-term neurodegenerative changes.

Reduced BDNF levels correlate with impaired synaptic stability and increased susceptibility to neuronal damage (Makin et al., 2007). These findings align with Glumac et al. (2017), who observed hippocampal damage following chronic GC exposure.

Acute GC administration facilitates glutamate release, improving neuronal communication. However, chronic elevation of GC levels induces excitotoxic stress, leading to hippocampal neuronal injury. Furthermore, sustained GC exposure suppresses hippocampal neurogenesis via BDNF inhibition and impairs mitochondrial function, resulting in oxidative stress and diminished energy production.

Van Marle et al. (2013) demonstrated that moderate hydrocortisone doses enhance memory performance by increasing neuronal activity within the hippocampus. Conversely, chronic exposure to high GC levels reduces neurogenesis and hippocampal volume and increases vulnerability to neuronal apoptosis through oxidative damage and mitochondrial dysfunction. Studies by Coluccia et al. (2008) and Glumac et al. (2017) corroborate those high doses of prednisone and dexamethasone lead to long-term memory deficits associated with hippocampal structural impairment.

At low to moderate concentrations, GCs support synaptic plasticity (Coluccia et al., 2008). Moreover, administration of moderate hydrocortisone doses (30 mg) has been shown to improve memory performance under stress by enhancing signal transmission and connectivity in the prefrontal cortex (Hurlemann et al., 2007).

4.4.2 Hormonal regulation and Neurochemical Dynamics

The prefrontal cortex (PFC) plays a pivotal role in executive functions, including attention, planning, and decision-making (Hathaway et al., 2024). However, chronic exposure to GCs leads to dysregulation of dopamine and glutamate signaling pathways, resulting in impaired synaptic integrity and reduced long-term potentiation (LTP). Mason et al. (2018) demonstrated that excessive GC exposure correlates with decreased signal transmission efficacy in the PFC.

Wingenfeld et al. (2011) reported that overactivation of GR impairs working memory, likely due to the overload of neural networks. This impairment is hypothesized to involve a reduction in dendritic complexity, negatively affecting LTP. Supporting this, Bremner et al. (2004) found that chronic GC exposure diminishes stress adaptability and compromises neuronal resilience.

These findings align with the concept of allostatic load, which describes the cumulative cognitive and physiological consequences of prolonged stress exposure. While this framework captures various stress responses, current models may inadequately address the intricate interactions among multiple neurochemical systems. An extended model could consider the interplay between GCs and other neurotransmitter systems such as dopamine and serotonin, which likely interact synergistically with cortisol to modulate cognitive outcomes.

5. Quality Assessment of Included Studies

This section provides an evaluation of the quality of the included studies, with particular attention to the methodologies and measurement tools employed.

5.1 Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool

To assess the methodological quality of the included studies, the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool (RoB 2.0) was employed. This instrument evaluates a potential bias risks across five key categories: (1) randomization process, (2) blinding of participants and personnel, (3) completeness of outcome data, (4) measurement of outcomes, and (5) selective reporting (The Cochrane Collaboration, 2024).

Each category was reviewed for the risk of bias for each study and classified into "low risk", "moderately high risk" or "high risk".

The overall methodological assessment indicates that most studies demonstrate a low risk of bias (see Table 4). All studies utilized randomized designs, and no risk of bias was identified in the randomization domain, justifying a low-risk classification for all.

Blinding was implemented in most studies, minimizing the likelihood of measurement errors and observer bias. Exceptions include the studies by Grossmann et al. (2006) and Ottens et al. (2014), where blinding of researchers was not documented, resulting in a moderate risk of detection bias. Despite this, the findings generally exhibit consistent effects regarding dose-response relationships and cognitive outcomes such as memory and attention.

Some heterogeneity was noted in results, particularly in studies by Hurlemann et al. (2007) and Hinkelmann et al. (2015), which may be attributable to differences in study populations (e.g., elderly versus younger adults) and clinical contexts (e.g., postoperative settings). This leads to moderate consistency of evidence, underscoring the importance of considering contextual and demographic variables in interpreting outcomes.

Attrition and data completeness were adequately reported in most studies, resulting in predominantly low risk of bias in this domain. However, studies by Lenze et al. (2014), Grossmann et al. (2006), Young et al. (2004), Hinkelmann et al. (2015), and Belanoff et al. (2002) showed incomplete attrition reporting, corresponding to a moderate risk of bias.

All studies employed standardized, validated, and objective methods to assess cognitive functions, ensuring low risk of bias in outcome measurement. The evidence is direct, as these studies specifically investigated the effects of GC interventions on cognitive domains, primarily memory and attention.

Precision of findings varies while several studies provide robust and precise estimates, the majority are limited by relatively small sample sizes and short follow-up durations, which constrains the evaluation of long-term effects. Consequently, the overall precision rating is moderate. Larger, longitudinal studies or meta-analyses are warranted to enhance evidence strength.

Reporting bias was assessed as low across all studies due to transparent and comprehensive result presentation without indication of selective outcome reporting.

In summary, the methodological quality of the included studies ranges from moderate to high. Most studies exhibit low risk of bias across assessed domains, providing consistent, direct, and reliable evidence on GC effects on cognition. Identified limitations primarily relate to population heterogeneity and incomplete reporting in a subset of studies. Nevertheless, the randomized controlled trial designs underpin the robustness of these findings.

5.2 Methodological Techniques and Measurement Methods

The included studies employed diverse methodological approaches to investigate the effects of GCs on cognitive function. These approaches can be categorized into four main types: neuropsychological testing, neuroimaging techniques, hormonal assessments, and behavior-based experimental paradigms. Each method offers distinct strengths and limitations, which are summarized in Table 5.

5.2.1 Neuropsychological Tests

Neuropsychological testing represents the most frequently used approach for the objective assessment of cognitive function (see Table 5). Several studies, including those by Lenze et al. (2014) and Valentin et al. (2016), utilized comprehensive neuropsychological test batteries characterized by multiple measurement time points and detailed cognitive assessments, such as the Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test (RAVLT).

Other investigations, such as Donoghue et al. (2020) and Vaz et al. (2011), applied the Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB), which provides computerized, standardized measures particularly focusing on working memory domains. The Confusion Assessment Method (CAM), used by Sakic et al. (2023) to evaluate POCD, exemplifies integration of cognitive testing with physiological markers.

The principal strengths of these neuropsychological instruments include their validated sensitivity to subtle cognitive changes induced by GCs high standardization, and applicability across diverse populations. However, a notable limitation is that these assessments typically offer only cross-sectional snapshots of cognitive performance and may be influenced by confounding factors such as circadian rhythms or transient mood states. Furthermore, these tests generally do not capture long-term cognitive effects, which are of relevance in clinical contexts (Talebi et al., 2020; Zaytseva et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2018).

5.2.2 Imaging Techniques

To investigate the structural and functional effects of GCs on the brain, imaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and positron emission tomography (PET) have been used in some studies. Studies such as those by Hurlemann et al. (2007) and Coluccia et al. (2008) show that these techniques allow for precise mapping of GC-induced changes in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex, which are central to memory and cognitive flexibility.

Some studies, including Grossmann et al. (2006), combine functional imaging with peripheral hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis measurements, offering comprehensive insights into the neuroendocrine mechanisms underlying GC effects. Multimodal approaches, such as those by Van Marle et al. (2013), integrate polysomnography and MRI to deepen understanding of memory consolidation processes.

Further studies, such as Belanoff et al. (2002) and Fang et al. (2014), utilize an integrated approach combining objective neuropsychological assessments with subjective reports and physiological markers. This comprehensive methodology facilitates detailed investigation of the relationship between HPA axis function and cognitive outcomes. Additionally, multicenter studies with strict definitions of POCD, exemplified by Bremner et al. (2004) and Ottens et al. (2014), enhance the generalizability and robustness of findings.

Nevertheless, a major methodological limitation across many studies is the lack of standardized, long-term follow-up, which hampers the evaluation of sustained GC effects on cognition.

The strengths of neuroimaging lie in their capacity to visualize neuronal activity and structural changes in vivo with high spatial resolution. However, these methods are resource-intensive, requiring considerable time, specialized equipment, and technical expertise, which can limit their broader applicability (Morzelewski et al., 2011).

5.2.3 Hormonal Measurements

Hormonal assessments, particularly the quantification of cortisol concentrations in saliva, blood, or urine, have been widely utilized to monitor both endogenous and exogenous GC levels. Studies such as Buning et al. (2015) and Chae et al. (2019) illustrate that cortisol measurements offer valuable complementary data on biologically active hormone levels, which correlate directly with cognitive functions including memory and attention.

The main strength of hormonal measurements lies in their capacity to objectively quantify the biological substrate underlying GC effects. Longitudinal sampling, for example through repeated saliva collection, enables chronological tracking of hormone exposure and dynamic changes over time.

However, this method is limited by the considerable intra- and inter-individual variability of cortisol secretion, which can be influenced by extrinsic factors such as sleep quality, dietary intake, and acute stress (El-Farhan et al., 2013). This variability poses challenges for cross-subject comparability and may confound interpretation of the relationship between cortisol levels and cognitive outcomes.

5.2.4 Quality Assessment Summary

The methodological approaches employed across the included studies complement each other by balancing respective strengths and limitations. Neuropsychological tests provide a cost-effective and straightforward means of detecting cognitive changes, while imaging techniques offer in-depth insights into the neurobiological substrates and mechanisms underlying GC effects. Hormonal measurements enable direct quantification of GC exposure, facilitating the linkage between hormone levels and cognitive outcomes.

Taken together, the integration of these diverse methodologies yields a more comprehensive understanding of GC impacts on cognitive function. Enhancing the use of multimodal assessment strategies in future research could further elucidate the complex mechanisms of GC action.

Moreover, future studies should prioritize longitudinal designs with extended follow-up periods and recruit more diverse cohorts with respect to age and gender to improve the generalizability and clinical relevance of findings.

6. Discussion

This section interprets the findings within the framework of existing theoretical models and empirical evidence. The research questions posed are addressed, and the methodological limitations identified throughout the review are critically examined. Furthermore, possible reasons for inconsistencies and contradictions in GC research are explored, considering factors such as study design, population heterogeneity, and varying GC dosages. This discussion aims to provide a balanced synthesis of current knowledge while highlighting areas requiring further investigation.

6.1 Results on the Effects of Glucocorticoids on Cognitive Function

The findings of this thesis demonstrate that the effects of GCs on cognitive function are both dose- and context-dependent. The corticosteroid receptor hypothesis (McEwen, 1968) and the allostatic load theory (McEwen, 2007) provide a theoretical framework to explain these observations. Low to moderate doses of GCs primarily activate mineralocorticoid receptors, which are associated with neuroprotective mechanisms such as memory consolidation and enhanced neuronal plasticity. These processes likely underlie the beneficial effects of GCs on memory observed in certain conditions, such as moderate stress (Van Marle et al., 2013; Wingfeld et al., 2011). In contrast, higher doses predominantly activate GC- receptors, which can induce neurotoxic effects and contribute to cognitive impairments, especially with chronic exposure. These detrimental effects, particularly impacting memory and attention are well supported by empirical studies (Coluccia et al., 2008; Mason et al., 2018).

6.1.1 Positive Effects of Glucocorticoids

Moderate doses of GCs have been demonstrated to facilitate the prioritization of emotional memory. Research by Van Marle et al. (2013) and Hurlmann et al. (2007) indicates that GCs enhance the selective encoding and consolidation of emotionally salient information via increased functional connectivity between the amygdala and the hippocampus. These mechanisms may represent evolutionarily adaptive processes that prioritize emotionally

relevant stimuli. Complementary findings by Buning et al. (2015) and Hinkelmann et al. (2015) further report improvements in attention following administration of targeted hydrocortisone doses. Such insights suggest promising therapeutic avenues, particularly for individuals experiencing cognitive impairments associated with stress-related disorders.

6.1.2 Negative Effect of Glucocorticoids

Conversely, high doses of GCs have been associated with detrimental cognitive effects. Studies by Jose Vaz et al. (2011) and Mason et al. (2018) have documented neurotoxic impacts, including impairments in executive functions and working memory. Prolonged exposure to elevated GC levels can induce structural alterations in the hippocampus and potentially trigger neurodegenerative processes. These findings bear significant clinical relevance, particularly for individuals suffering from chronic stress or PTSD. Jose Vaz et al. (2011) demonstrated that high-dose hydrocortisone administration impairs working memory, especially in tasks requiring planning and inhibitory control. These impairments were attributed to diminished capacity for encoding multimodal information and maintaining it within the phonological loop. Similarly, Mason et al. (2018) reported that long-term treatment with megestrol leads to a significant decline in declarative memory performance, further supporting the hypothesis that sustained elevated GC exposure fosters neurodegeneration.

6.1.3 Unclear or Absent Effect

Some studies, such as those by Wingenfeld et al. (2011) and Chae et al. (2019), reported no significant impact of GCs on cognitive function. Wingenfeld et al. found that elevated cortisol levels did not impair working memory or cognitive flexibility, while Chae et al. examined the isolated and combined effects of hydrocortisone and yohimbine on spatial learning without observing clear cognitive deficits. These findings challenge the notion of cortisol as a universal modulator of cognitive processes.

The observed inconsistencies may result from methodological variability, including differences in testing paradigms, GC dosage, timing, or characteristics of the study populations. This heterogeneity underscores the need for more rigorous and standardized research protocols.

Clarifying the dose-response relationship is crucial to delineate a potential "therapeutic window" in which beneficial cognitive effects of GCs can be harnessed while minimizing adverse outcomes

6.2 Results on the influencing factors: dose, duration of use, individual differences

The impact of GCs on cognitive function is modulated by several factors, including dosage, duration of administration, individual characteristics (such as age, psychological status, and genetic variability), and timing of hormone delivery. For instance, older adults in postoperative settings benefit cognitively from moderate GC doses, whereas chronic high-dose exposure correlates with cognitive decline (Valentin et al., 2016).

Timing of administration emerges as a critical factor: Chae et al. (2019) and Glumac et al. (2017) report neuroprotective effects following preoperative moderate dosing, while intraoperative high doses do not confer similar benefits. The nature and temporal pattern of hormonal stimulation significantly shape GC-induced cognitive outcomes (see Fig. 6).

Vulnerable populations, particularly individuals with PTSD, exhibit heightened sensitivity to GCs due to dysregulated receptor dynamics and diminished hippocampal neuronal resilience (Grossmann et al., 2006). Age-related neurodegenerative processes further exacerbate the detrimental effects of chronic GC elevation on the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus (Hinkelmann et al., 2015). Conversely, moderate doses may exert neuroprotective actions in specific clinical contexts like the postoperative phase (Valentin et al., 2016).

The mechanisms underlying POCD prevention by dexamethasone remain incompletely elucidated. Valentin et al. (2016) propose that neuroprotection may be mediated by reduced inflammatory markers, such as S100 β protein. However, findings by Ottens et al. (2014) suggest that anti-inflammatory effects alone are insufficient for effective POCD prevention. Glumac et al. (2017) suggest possible long-term benefits, yet robust, statistically significant evidence remains lacking. It is unclear whether observed effects are drug-specific or influenced by confounding factors.

Future research should prioritize large-scale, multicenter studies to validate these findings. Incorporating biomarker profiles, including genetic analyses, could improve assessment of individual susceptibility to GCs effects.

Figure 5. Dose-response relationship of Glucocorticoids on cognitive functions

This figure illustrates the dose-response relationship of glucocorticoids on cognitive performance based on the reviewed literature. The effects are categorized into three main dose ranges:

- 1. Low doses (up to approximately 25mg):**
Cognitive effects, particularly on memory and attention, are generally positive in this range (see Hurlmann et al., 2007; Valentin et al., 2016; Tiemensma et al., 2016; Hinkelmann et al., 2015)
- 2. Moderate doses (approximately 25–50mg):**
Supportive effects on memory consolidation are evident, especially in stress-related contexts. This dose range corresponds to the peak of beneficial cognitive effects (cf. Van Marle et al., 2013).
- 3. High doses (above 50mg):**
Adverse effects, including memory impairment and increased vulnerability to neurocognitive disorders, have been reported in this range (cf. Wingenfeld et al., 2011).

6.3 Results on the Neurobiological Mechanisms of Synthetic Glucocorticoids

The dual receptor hypothesis offers a robust framework for explaining the divergent cognitive effects of GCs. At moderate cortisol levels, MR are predominantly activated, supporting adaptive stress responses and facilitating memory consolidation. In contrast GR) are activated at higher concentrations and are associated with neurotoxic effects and cognitive impairment. This receptor-specific mechanism aligns with findings from Cornelisse et al. (2011) and Mason et al. (2018), which highlight the interaction between the amygdala and hippocampus in emotional memory formation.

Prolonged GR activation contributes to hippocampal atrophy, as well as dysregulation of the HPA axis, resulting in allostatic overload, a central mechanism in stress-related cognitive decline.

On the cellular level, studies such as those by Coluccia et al. (2008) and Glumac et al. (2017) demonstrate that chronic exposure to high-dose GCs impairs synaptic integrity in both the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus. These alterations manifest in reduced cognitive flexibility and working memory capacity, likely due to compromised neuronal plasticity and reduced synaptogenesis. Persistent GC elevation further interferes with neuronal regeneration and disrupts glutamate homeostasis, leading to excitotoxicity and mitochondrial dysfunction—both implicated in neurodegeneration

Beyond receptor-mediated effects, epigenetic mechanisms have emerged as key modulators of long-term GC-induced cognitive changes. For instance, Jones et al. (2024) report hypermethylation of promoter regions of the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) gene following prolonged GC exposure. This epigenetic modification impairs synaptic plasticity and correlates with hippocampal-dependent memory deficits, pointing to a possible mechanistic link between GC treatment and structural brain changes.

These findings underscore the necessity of dose- and context-specific application of synthetic GCs to avoid unintended cognitive side effects. Furthermore, they highlight the importance of future studies that employ multimodal imaging techniques, such as fMRI and PET, to visualize functional changes in memory-related brain regions across varying GC doses and treatment durations. Such investigations may contribute to the development of neuroprotective interventions aimed at mitigating the adverse cognitive consequences of GC therapy.

The neurobiological mechanisms underlying the cognitive effects of GCs encompass a range of interrelated processes, including the modulation of gene expression, increased glutamate release, excitotoxicity, and mitochondrial dysfunction. These molecular and cellular alterations contribute to disrupted synaptic signaling, reduced neuroplasticity, and ultimately, cognitive impairment. Such findings underscore the necessity for a dose- and context-specific application of GCs in clinical settings, to minimize adverse cognitive effects and prevent long-term neurological damage.

Emerging evidence, such as that reported by Jones et al. (2024), suggests that epigenetic mechanism may critically mediate the long-term consequences of GC exposure. Specifically, hypermethylation of promoter regions in the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) gene has been associated with decreased BDNF expression, impairing synaptic plasticity and neuronal resilience, particularly in the hippocampus. These epigenetic modifications may represent a key mechanism through which chronic GC exposure exerts lasting negative effects on memory and cognitive function.

Taken together, these insights not only refine our understanding of GC action on brain structure and function, but also open new avenues for research into preventive strategies and individualized treatment protocols. In particular, the integration of molecular biomarkers, epigenetic profiling, and advanced neuroimaging could facilitate the development of targeted interventions to mitigate GC-induced cognitive decline.

6.4 Explanation of Contradictions and Contrasts in the Field of Research

The present analysis reveals several methodological limitations within the existing literature that substantially constrain the interpretability of findings. A central issue is the prevalence of cross-sectional study designs, which provide only temporal snapshots and do not allow for causal inferences regarding the relationship between GC exposure and cognitive outcomes. As a result, it remains uncertain whether observed cognitive impairments are directly attributable to GC administration or reflect pre-existing vulnerabilities or unmeasured confounders.

A further source of inconsistency arises from the marked heterogeneity in GC dosage and duration across studies. This variability complicates the comparability of findings and undermines efforts to derive generalizable conclusions. While some studies examine low-dose applications that predominantly activate MR, potentially promoting neuroplastic and memory-

supportive processes, others focus on high doses that activate GR, which are associated with neurotoxic effects. The lack of a standardized dosing framework is therefore a critical barrier to the development of a coherent body of evidence.

In addition, many studies are characterized by limited sample sizes, which reduce statistical power and limit external validity. This is particularly problematic in clinical research involving vulnerable populations, where interindividual differences—such as age, gender, genetic polymorphisms, and psychosocial stress levels, may significantly modulate HPA axis function and influence sensitivity to GCs. These individual differences likely contribute to the heterogeneous results observed in the literature.

The interaction between MR and GR receptors is another underexplored factor that may underlie contradictory findings. A more nuanced investigation of receptor dynamics, particularly using *in vivo* studies with healthy and clinical cohorts, could help clarify how receptor co-activation or imbalance contributes to cognitive outcomes following GC exposure. Another critical gap in the literature is the lack of longitudinal data. Most studies assess only acute or short-term effects, thereby neglecting the long-term neurobiological consequences of chronic GC exposure. Longitudinal research is essential for capturing progressive structural and functional brain changes, particularly in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex, which are central to memory and executive function.

Moreover, environmental and psychosocial stressors, such as chronic stress or traumatic life events, represent additional modulating factors that can dysregulate the HPA axis. These variables may amplify or buffer GC effects and thus further contribute to inconsistent findings across studies.

Finally, gender differences remain a largely neglected factor in GC research. Many studies disproportionately sample male participants, thereby limiting the generalizability of results to female populations. Given those hormonal fluctuations, e.g., across the menstrual cycle, can influence GCs sensitivity and receptor expression, gender-specific responses to GCs may be systematically underestimated. Addressing this bias in future research is essential for developing more precise and inclusive models of GC action.

7. Classification of Previous Findings in Clinical Applications

The findings of the reviewed studies provide important insights into the effects of GCs on cognitive domains such as attention and memory. The evidence suggests that targeted modulation of GC activity may represent a promising therapeutic strategy for mitigating cognitive deficits, particularly in patient groups with dysregulated cortisol levels, such as older adults or individuals with PTSD.

However, the clinical implementation of such approaches remains complex due to substantial interindividual variability in HPA axis regulation and stress reactivity. Personalized treatment strategies are therefore required, which consider not only patient-specific physiological profiles but also potential differences in receptor sensitivity and response patterns. In this context, further research is needed to define optimal dosing protocols, timing of administration, and individual risk–benefit ratios.

Preliminary concepts, such as the combination of low-dose GCs with selective GR antagonists, may offer a path toward balancing therapeutic efficacy with the minimization of neurocognitive side effects. However, this approach remains largely experimental and requires validation through longitudinal and controlled clinical trials.

The findings by Lenze et al. (2014) point to possible age- and population-specific effects: in elderly patients with anxiety disorders, elevated cortisol levels were associated with improved cognitive performance, highlighting the need for differentiated clinical application based on patient characteristics.

Regarding attentional processes, the relationship with GC exposure appears non-linear and context sensitive. While acute elevations in cortisol during stress can enhance selective attention and cognitive focus, prolonged or excessive GC exposure is associated with impairments in executive function, working memory, and sustained attention.

An increasingly relevant factor in the cognitive impact of GCs is the interaction between hormonal and immunological pathways. Chronic inflammation, often accompanied by elevated cortisol levels, may impair synaptic plasticity and promote neuronal degradation, thus

contributing to long-term cognitive decline. This underscores the importance of investigating the triadic interplay between cortisol, inflammatory markers (e.g., IL-6, TNF- α), and neurocognitive performance.

Particularly in conditions such as PTSD and bipolar disorder, GCs may exert therapeutic neuroprotective or regulatory effects, whereas in other psychiatric disorders their efficacy may be limited or even detrimental. A more refined understanding of disorder-specific mechanisms and biomarker-guided stratification will be essential to enable the safe and effective translation of GC-based interventions into clinical practice.

A central focus of future research should be the interindividual variability in the cognitive response to GCs. Genetic polymorphisms, particularly those affecting GC receptor density, sensitivity, and downstream signaling pathways, may contribute to differential treatment outcomes. Moreover, functional differences in the regulation of the HPA axis could explain varying susceptibilities to both the beneficial and adverse cognitive effects of GCs.

Sex-specific differences in hormone regulation and GC sensitivity also warrant greater attention. Hormonal fluctuations across the menstrual cycle, menopause-related endocrine shifts, or differing GR/MR expression profiles between men and women may modulate the cognitive response to GC treatment. These factors have been underrepresented in many previous studies, limiting the generalizability of the findings.

Consequently, future clinical trials should incorporate stratified subgroup analyses based on genetic, biological, and psychosocial markers. This would enable the development of personalized therapeutic strategies that optimize GC efficacy while minimizing the risk of cognitive impairment.

Additionally, the harmonization of methodological standards, including the use of standardized cognitive assessment tools, uniform dosing protocols, and consistent timing of administration, is essential to enhance comparability between studies and improve the clinical translatability of research findings. Only through such coordinated efforts can GC-based interventions be tailored to meet the nuanced needs of diverse patient populations.

8. Limitations

Despite adherence to the PRISMA guidelines, several limitations may affect the validity and generalizability of this literature review. While PRISMA offers a robust framework for conducting systematic reviews, it does not eliminate the risk of selection bias. For instance, publication bias remains a potential concern, as unpublished studies or grey literature were not included. Additionally, non-English-language studies were excluded, which may have led to an underrepresentation of relevant international findings.

The search strategy was limited to selected databases, which increases the risk of omitting pertinent studies, particularly those published in specialized or regional journals. This may restrict the completeness and comprehensiveness of the findings and thus limit their external validity.

Furthermore, the assessment of study quality was conducted using the RoB 2.0 tool. While this instrument is widely accepted for evaluating the risk of bias in randomized studies, its application is partly dependent on the subjective judgment of the reviewers, especially in domains such as the assessment of randomization processes, blinding procedures, and outcome reporting. This introduces the potential for evaluation bias, particularly when study documentation is incomplete or ambiguous.

In sum, the outlined limitations should be considered when interpreting the results of this review. They underscore the need for more transparent reporting standards, multilingual inclusion strategies, and broader database searches in future systematic reviews to minimize bias and enhance reproducibility.

9. Conclusion and Outlook

The present findings underscore that the effects of GCs on cognitive functions are highly dose-dependent and significantly modulated by individual factors such as genetic variations, age, psychological stress, and hormonal sensitivity. While short-term, moderate GC administration can enhance attention and memory, particularly under stress-induced conditions, long-term, high-dose exposure is associated with neurotoxic effects, including impairments in working memory, executive function, and structural brain integrity.

The mechanistic basis for these effects lies in the differential activation of MR and GR, along with changes in synaptic plasticity, glutamate-mediated excitotoxicity, and epigenetic modifications, particularly in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex.

However, critical research gaps remain, particularly with respect to:

1. Long-term consequences of GC exposure on brain structure and function
2. Mechanisms of HPA axis dysregulation, including impaired receptor feedback loops
3. Individual susceptibility factors, such as receptor polymorphisms and epigenetic signatures (e.g., methylation of the BDNF gene), which may explain differential responses to GC therapy.

Key Priorities for Future Research:

- Longitudinal studies are needed to establish causal relationships between GC exposure and cognitive decline, ideally with observation periods spanning several years.
- Biomarker-based approaches should be developed to predict individual sensitivity. This includes genetic markers such as NR3C1 polymorphisms, which may influence GC receptor function.
- Innovative therapeutic strategies, such as the co-administration of GCs with neuroprotective agents or selective GR antagonists, should be systematically investigated in clinical trials.
- The use of advanced imaging techniques (e.g., real-time fMRI, PET) may help detect subtle GC-induced changes in brain function not captured by traditional neuropsychological assessments.

- Future clinical studies should be multicenter and sufficiently powered ($n > 200$), with stratification by age, sex, and psychiatric diagnosis to increase external validity.
- Standardization of dosage protocols and cognitive testing methods will be crucial to improving cross-study comparability.

Finally, a refined theoretical framework, such as the three-phase dose-response model (see Fig. 5), offers a promising foundation for predicting cognitive outcomes based on GC dosage and duration of administration. While acute effects may be transient and reversible, chronic exposure appears to lead to structural and functional impairments that warrant further investigation.

Conclusion

This thesis has illuminated key findings regarding the cognitive effects of GCs and identified important gaps in current research. Addressing these gaps will require interdisciplinary collaboration, integration of molecular and neuroimaging data, and a move toward personalized treatment approaches that balance therapeutic benefits with neurocognitive safety.

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Appendix A: Evaluation of studies according to RoB 2.0 criteria

Table 4: Quality assessment according to RoB 2.0 criteria

Study	Rando- mizatio n	Ver- blindung	Data Completeness	Measurin g the results	Reportin g	Overall bias risk
Chae et al. 2019	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Lenze et al. 2014	Small	Small	Moderate	Small	Small	Moderate
Grossmann et al. 2006	Small	Moderate	Moderate	Small	Small	Moderate
Van Marle et al. 2013	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Mason et al. 2018	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Coluccia et al. 2008	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Valentin et al. 2016	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Glumac et al., 2017	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Young et al. 2004	Small	Small	Moderate	Small	Small	Moderate
Gallagher et al. 2004	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Wingenfeld et al. 2011	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Jose Vaz et al. 2011	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Hurle- mann et al. 2007	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small

Hinkelman n et al. 2015	Small	Small	Moderate	Small	Small	Moderate
Golier et al. 2015	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Ottens et al. 2014	Small	Moderate	Moderate	Small	Small	Moderate
Cornelisse et al. 2011	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Wood et al. 2014	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Yehuda et al. 2010	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Bremner et al. 2004	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Buning et al. 2015	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small
Belanoff et al. 2002	Small	Small	Moderate	Small	Small	Moderate
Chae et al. 2019	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small	Small

Appendix B: Overview of the measurement methods used

Table 5: Overview of the measurement methods used within the studies

Study	Neuropsychological Tests	Imaging techniques	Hormonal measurements
Chae et al. 2019	Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test (RAVLT)	None	Speichel-Cortisol
Lenze et al. 2014	Mini-Mental-State Examination (MMSE), Trail Making Test (TMT)	None	None
Grossmann et al. 2006	Verbal Memory Test	None	None
Van Marle et al. 2013	Auditory and Visual Memory Test	None	Speichel-Cortisol
Mason et al. 2018	Declarative Memory Test	None	None
Coluccia et al. 2008	Verbal Learning and Memory Test	fMR)	Speichel-Cortisol
Valentin et al. 2016	MMSE, Trail Making Test (TMT)	None	Blut-Cortisol
Glumac et al. 2017	Cognitive Battery Tests for Memory and Attention	None	None
Young et al. 2004	Working Memory Task	None	None
Gallagher et al. 2004	Spatial Working Memory Test	None	None
Wingenfeld et al. 2011	Digit Span Test, Trail Making Test (TMT)	None	Speichel-Cortisol
Jose Vaz et al. 2011	Working Memory Task	None	Speichel-Cortisol

Hurlemann et al. 2007	Episodic Memory Task	fMRI	Speichel-Cortisol
Hinkelman n et al. 2015	Verbal and Non-verbal Memory Test	None	Blut-Cortisol
Golier et al. 2015	Verbal Learning Test, Working Memory Test	None	None
Ottens et al. 2014	Cognitive Battery Tests für POCD	None	None
Cornelisse et al. 2011	Selective Attention Task, Working Memory Task	None	Speichel-Cortisol
Wood et al. 2014	No specific cognitive tests specified	None	None
Yehuda et al. 2010	Memory and hippocampal test battery	None	None
Bremner et al. 2004	Verbal Memory Test	None	None
Buning et al. 2015	Memory und Attention Battery	None	Speichel-Cortisol
Belanoff et al. 2002	Memory and attention test battery	None	None